
THE IMPACT OF THE MARKET OF EDUCATIONAL SERVICES ON THE INNOVATIVE DEVELOPMENT OF THE NATIONAL ECONOMY

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In the strategy of any society related to economic development, special attention is paid to the formation of the national innovation system. The concept of the national innovation system as an important sign of the economy entered science in the 70s of the XX century, and this concept is defined differently in different sources.

For example, in the materials of the Organization for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD) (1997) there are definitions that are close to each other in terms of meaning, in which the national innovation system is an individual and interdependent development and dissemination of new technologies at the level of a particular country, private and public. It is described as a set of institutions belonging to sectors.

According to K. Freeman, the national innovation system is a complex system of economic entities and social institutions (values, norms, rights) that participate in the development, storage, distribution and transformation of new knowledge into new technologies in the creation of new technologies, products and services consumed by society.

The national innovative system in the socio-economic development of countries, the national innovative economy based on the idea of Y. Schumpeter, the development trends of the post-industrial society based on the American scientist D. Bell, the knowledge economy or creative economy theory of J. Hawkins, in the scientific works of Y. Benkler called "Digital Economy" It is also reflected in the results of research such as the network economy advanced in the mentioned concepts and the digital economy introduced by D. Tapscott. In today's national innovative development of Uzbekistan, the concept of digital economy is being promoted, and the possibilities of achieving it based on the development of the higher education system have been shown.

In the conditions of today's rise of the world economy, most countries are choosing an innovative way of development as the main factor for achieving sustainable economic growth and a high standard of living of the population.

Business practice shows that the development of innovative activities is one of the conditions for the modernization of the economy and is considered a necessary factor for the acceleration of market relations.

Today, every country, regardless of the level of scientific, technological and socio-economic development, based on the general principles of innovation, takes into account the scientific and technological potential, the state of labor and raw material reserves, natural and climatic conditions, the peculiarities of its economy, etc. should strive to create.

The government of the Republic of Uzbekistan is taking effective measures to preserve the scientific potential, reform the field of science and direct it to solving current socio-economic problems. In this regard, special attention is paid to the role of the higher education system and its science development in the development of the national innovative system. In this regard, the development of higher education and its science, strengthening of the country's scientific and technological potential, is considered a necessary condition for the step-by-step transition of the economy to consistent innovative development.

In 2016, in order to create an effective innovation system that increases the technological level and production competitiveness, brings innovative products to the domestic and foreign markets, develops import substitution production, accelerates socio-economic growth, and helps achieve national strategic goals, in 2016 development program" was developed and approved.

The main goal of this program is "...effective use of advanced scientific, technical and technological achievements, increasing the competitiveness of innovative technologies and products, rational use of natural raw materials and investment resources, economic, energy, food and environmental security and the lifestyle of other people is the formation of a national innovation system that creates favorable conditions for the rise.

Introducing the principles of national innovative development into the economic sphere is an effective and convenient objective opportunity for the development of the market of educational services and its main subjects - higher education institutions. Important trends in today's world economy are to turn innovation into the main source of development and to strengthen the role of human capital in this, in which the development of the mechanism of interaction of the factors of the national innovation system is a large-scale and complex task. It will be possible only through well-thought-out, mutually agreed effective actions of the state, business, economic and scientific communities. It is known from some studies that if previously the level of socio-economic development of some

countries was mainly assessed by their existing natural resources, in the conditions of the innovative model of the economy, new technologies and intellectual capital adapted to innovative development are of priority.

In developed countries, the industrialized economy is turning into an information economy or a knowledge economy, and the current educational models are not keeping up with the coming changes. This ultimately creates differences between the state of the existing education system and the dynamics of socio-economic development. Progress can only be achieved if existing educational models are compatible with innovative development activities in all areas.

In recent years, in many countries of the world, due to the efforts of state bodies in the development of the economy, the attention to the problem of the development of the higher education system and the market of educational services is increasing. Improving the quality of education is a necessary means of ensuring the improvement of the national innovation system and the development of the country's economy. Therefore, the economic policy of the developed countries of the world is aimed at the development and implementation of the concept of innovative development in the market of educational services.

Current conditions bring the concept of national competitiveness of economics to the leading position in the assessment of the development of the countries of the world. In this regard, the educational system plays a decisive role in achieving innovative development and increasing the economic competitiveness of countries in the world economy.

Studies focused on the process of determining the national competitiveness ratings of the countries of the world have proven that the effective functioning of the education system is an important factor affecting the country's competitiveness and economic growth, as well as the increase in the population's well-being.

The global or global competitiveness index of the countries of the world covers three sub-indices and they are based on indicators of twelve main groups.

Higher education has a significant impact on the effective development of the labor market, the development of various social institutions and entrepreneurship in society. Among them, higher education is the most important factor in ensuring the country's national competitiveness in the international arena, and therefore special attention should be paid to the development of this sector.

The stable development of all stages of the higher education system is an important and indispensable condition for the development of the country and society. The comprehensive development of higher education is an important condition for the economic growth of countries striving for skilled production,

technological, innovative and technical development. This situation is gaining importance in the context of the development of global and integration processes in the world economy. In addition, every country that wants to take an important place in the international division of labor and ensure the competitiveness of its products in the world market must have highly qualified specialists who can quickly adapt to the changing environment and provide measures to increase the competitiveness of the country's economy.

The results of the research of the innovative potential of the Republic of Uzbekistan show that there are serious problems that have a negative impact on the implementation of the socio-economic tasks set before the country according to some important criteria (Table 1).

Table 1

Indicators affecting the implementation of socio-economic tasks

No	Criteria	Indicator (score)
1	Patenting rate for inventions	0,8
2	The volume of expenses of enterprises and organizations for scientific researches and developments	3,2
3	Quality of work of research institutions	3,9

This is, first of all, the low rate of obtaining patents for various inventions (0.8 points), the low volume of expenditures by enterprises and organizations for scientific research and development (3.2 points), the low quality of the work of scientific research institutions in the republic (3.9 points) appears in such cases. In such conditions, it was necessary to rapidly develop and implement comprehensive research, measures on innovative development of the republic's economy.

REFERENCES:

1. "Innovative development program of the Republic of Uzbekistan in 2017-2021" 2016.
2. Benkler Y. The Wealth of Networks: How Social Production Transforms Markets and Freedom. New Haven, Conn.: Yale University Press, 2006. 515 p.
3. Tapscott D. The digital economy: promise and peril in the age of networked intelligence. New York; Montreal: McGraw-Hill, 1996. 342 p.

4. Schumpeter Y.A. Theory of economic development. Capitalism, socialism and democracy. M.: Eksmo, 2007. p. 862.

5. Howkins J. The Creative Economy: How People Make Money from Ideas. London: Penguin. 2001.